

FABRICATION AND THREE-POINT-BENDING BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC CURVED CORRUGATED SANDWICH PANEL WITH INTERFACE ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Three-point-bending behavior of glass fiber reinforced polypropylene curved corrugated sandwich panels taking account of the effects of core configurations and interface property were investigated by experimental method. The curved axial corrugated sandwich panels (CACSP) and curved circular corrugated sandwich panels (CCCSP) were fabricated by hot-press and adhesive bonding and also compared with the curved solid panel (CSP) with the same weight. Interface enhancement was implement by polypropylene glue stick insertion. The experiment results indicated that the polypropylene glue stick reinforcement is an effective method for curved axial corrugated sandwich panels. Compared with unenhanced ones, the peak load of polypropylene glue stick reinforced (PPRGS) CACSP is almost 2 times and the maximum displacement before failure extends to 8 times.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures have wide use in many fields such as aerospace, navigation, transporting and construction etc. for their excellent specific stiffness, strength and multi-functional properties [1]. Apart from flat ones, curved sandwich panels are also widely used as skins of ships, aerospace vehicles etc. Some studies of the curved sandwich panel with pyramidal truss core [2, 3], honeycomb core [4], pyramidal kagome core [5] and foam core [6-9] have been done.

Bending stiffness and strength play a vital role in determining the structural response of composite sandwich panels. Many studies about the bending behavior of flat composite sandwich panels with lattice cores have been reported [10-16], but most of which are concerned with fiber reinforced thermosetting composite. For fiber reinforced thermosetting composite sandwich panels subjected to three-point-bending, skin fracture tends to render the brittle failure of sandwich panel and leads to that the residual strength stays at a very low level comparing with the peak load [17, 18]. Schneider et al. [16] manufactured thermoplastic corrugated sandwich beams made from SrPET (Self-reinforced PET) with co-curing of core and face sheet. A ductile response after the peak load was found and meanwhile the load-displacement curve showed softening till a plateau load over the half of peak load was reached. This ductile response will be beneficial to the energy absorption capacity of thermoplastic sandwich panel.

The connection within a sandwich system includes adhesive bonding, mechanical fastening or a combination of both (known as hybrid bonding-fastening). Adhesive bonding is weight-saving and has lower fabrication cost, improved damage tolerance etc. [19, 20] while mechanical fastening offers the advantages of easier assembly and disassembly and insensitive to surface preparation and environmental factors [21]. Hybrid bonding-fastening joint is a selective technique that integrates the advantages of adhesive bonding and mechanical fastening and finds its wider application in many industry fields [22]. Apart from the simple adhesive bonding used to fabricate composite sandwich structures, many attempts have been made to enhance the adhesive bonding strength between face sheet and lattice core. Xiong et al. [23] added aluminum frames between face sheets and core and effectively enhanced the shear strength of composite lattice truss core. Fan et al. [24] fabricated

corrugated lattice truss composite sandwich panels and greatly enhance the shear strength of lattice sandwich panels without damaging the face sheet. Both of them enhance the interface strength by enlarging the contact area.

However, to the knowledge of the authors, no research work about the bending behavior of curved thermoplastic composite corrugated sandwich panel with lattice core has been reported. In present paper, the three-point-bending tests were conducted to investigate the bending resistance and behavior of glass fiber reinforced polypropylene (GFRPP) curved corrugated sandwich panels with two core configurations namely axial and circular ones and different interface connection techniques namely adhesive bonding and glue stick reinforcement. Firstly, the details of fabrication process and three-point-bending tests of curved corrugated sandwich panels are presented. Then, the bending resistance and failure modes of s and CCCSPs fabricated by adhesive bonding along with corresponding CSPs are investigated. Next, polypropylene glue stick reinforcement is introduced to CACSP and comparison is made between the reinforced ones and unreinforced ones. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

2 FABRICATION AND THREE-POINT-BENDING TESTS

2.1 Fabrication

Curved face sheet and two kinds of corrugated cores namely axial and circular were fabricated by hot press method. Both of counterparts were polished by sand paper and cleaned by ethyl alcohol, then bonded by adhesive MS1937 (Tonsan Adhesive, Inc.) after careful surface treatment and cured for 3 days with pressure. The property of adhesive and prepreg is listed in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. Afterwards, the curved sandwich panels were cut into final shape by CNC carving machine and the schematic is shown in Fig. 1.

Property	Value
Density	1.45 g/cm ³
Tack free time (@25C°, RH50%)	5-20 min
Cure speed (@25C°, RH50%)	4 mm/24h
Elongation at break (GB/T528)	>200%
Tensile strength (GB/T528)	3.0MPa
Shear strength (GB/T7124)	2.3MPa

Table 1: Adhesive property of MS1937 provided by Tonsan Adhesive, Inc..

Property	Value
Density	1.5 g/cm ³
Weight fraction of fibers	60%
Thickness	0.3 mm
Young's modulus in longitudinal direction	28 GPa
Young's modulus in transverse direction	3.2 GPa
In-plane shear modulus	946 MPa
In-plane Poisson's ratio	0.064
Longitudinal tensile strength	750 MPa
Longitudinal compressive strength	160 MPa
Transverse tensile strength	15 MPa
Transverse compressive strength	50 MPa

Table 2: Property of GFRPP prepreg provided by KINGFA Composites.

Figure 1: The fabrication of three kinds of curved panels.

The layup for both of face sheet and core is orthogonal as $[0/90]_3$. For comparison, the CSP with the same weight was also fabricated with orthogonal layup $[0/90]_{11}$. It should be noted that local fiber slip happened to the top layer whose direction was parallel to the circular direction during hot-pressing for CCCSP. This can be avoided by rearranging the layup of unifier prepreps to make the top and the bottom layers with axial direction or used woven fiber prepreps. In this paper, we still used the same layup for both CACSP and CCCSP for comparison.

The parameter of corrugated unit cell refers to [16] as shown in Fig. 2a with $h=19$ mm, $l=10$ mm and $\omega=60^\circ$. The relative density of the corrugated core can be calculated by Equation 1.

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{(h + l \sin \omega) t}{(h \cos \omega + l \sin \omega)(h + t)} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Schematic of (a) cross section of corrugated unit cell and (b) the three-point-bending specimen (take CACSP for example).

The length L and height H of the core are 230 mm and 24.4 mm. Though the width of unit cell is 42 mm, we set the width W to 52 mm in order to get wider adhesive zone for CCCSP and keep the same for CACSP and CSP. The length of the reinforced region L_0 in both ends is 30 mm. The parameters and mechanical property of specimens are listed in Table 3. Small dispersity of data is found and therefore the average of peak value and stiffness along with the corresponding coefficient of variation (COV) are also listed to compare the bending resistance of each configuration.

Specimen	Weight[g]	Relative density	Peak value[N]	Average peak value[N] (COV %)	Stiffness [N/mm]	Average stiffness [N/mm] (COV %)
CSP-1	144	/	2281		70	
CSP-2	146	/	2736	2559 (9.5)	87	80 (11.6)
CSP-3	150	/	2659		84	
CACSP-1	164	0.136	489		143	
CACSP-2	153	0.138	370	512 (30.2)	112	127 (12.4)
CACSP-3	158	0.138	677		125	
CCCSP-1	164	0.149	1420	1419 (0.1)	330	346 (6.6)
CCCSP-2	160	0.156	1417		363	
PPGSR			1122		96	
CACSP-1	163	0.112				
PPGSR			898	1013 (11.1)	90	88 (10.1)
CACSP-2	142	0.109				
PPGSR			1018		79	
CACSP-3	164	0.101				

Table 3: The parameters and mechanical property of specimens

2.2 Three-point-bending tests

Three-point-bending tests of the fabricated curved corrugated sandwich panels were conducted in electronic universal testing machine SANS CMT5105 (100kN) according to ASTM C393 with the loading speed of 2 mm/min. Load and displacement of indenter was recorded by built-in sensor in testing machine. Both ends of specimen were inserted with rigid foam and clamped by 3D-printed grips outside (Fig. 3) to prevent debonding in the edge. Core relative densities and specimen geometrical parameters were kept the same for the sake of comparison. Two or three specimens for each configuration were tested.

Figure 3: The three-point-bending test.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Adhesive bonding

Primarily, adhesive bonding is chosen to combine face sheet and core into sandwich structure for its efficiency and convenience with the method described in (Section 2.1). CACSP, CCCSP and CSP

were tested and load versus displacement curves were listed in Fig. 4. The peak force and stiffness for the above three configurations were listed in Table 3. For three CSP specimens cut from the same CSP sample, one failed due to delamination within the panel with the peak force 2281 N while other two failed due to fiber breaking in the center of panel with the peak force of 2736 N and 2659 N respectively. Stiffness varied from 70 N/mm to 87 N/mm. Note that the second specimen showed highest peak load and stiffness since it is in the center of sample where press and temperature are relatively well-distributed. Failure modes of three CSP specimens were shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4: The load versus displacement curves of three kinds of curved panels.

(a) Delamination and fiber breaking

(b) Fiber breaking

Figure 5: Failure modes of three CSP specimens.

For CACSP, similar relationship between load and displacement was found for three specimens—an initial linear stage followed by a strength degradation stage resulted from progressive shearing failure of adhesive as shown in Fig. 6 and 7. Sharp drops on curves appeared during degradation stage where every drop represented for a debonding between face sheet and unit cell. After each drop, the load rose gradually on account of face sheet bending till the next extreme load value. That debonding behavior initiated from the inward one and propagated to outermost one along with the loading of

upper pressure head resulting in the sidewise unit cell of axial corrugated core flipped instead of giving firm supporting against the load (Fig. 7). The axial corrugated core can recover after unloading with no visible damage which means the core hardly contribute much to the bending resistance of CACSP.

Figure 6: The load versus displacement curves of CACSPs.

Figure 7: The deformation modes of CACSP-3 (numbers correspond to those in Fig. 6).

The peak force and stiffness for three CACSP specimens varied from 370 N to 677 N and 112 N/mm to 143 N/mm. Compared with CSP, stiffness of CACSP increased by 60% while the peak force dropped nearly 80%. The face sheets are separated by core hence introducing higher cross sectional moment of inertia for sandwich structure and meanwhile weakening the structural strength in local loading condition due to material distribution. Hereby, CACSP is weaker but stiffer than CSP with the same mass.

For CCCSP, the peak force rose to about 1419 N with an obvious crack in the middle of circular core after which the force dropped down gradually till the local debonding took place resulting in a cliffy fall as shown (Fig. 8 and 9). Inherent higher bending stiffness compared with axial corrugated core makes it more strong against three-point-bending – 2.8 times in peak load and 2.7 times in stiffness. Though peak force decreased by 45%, CCCSP is almost 4.5 times the stiffness of corresponding CSP.

Figure 8: The load versus displacement curves of CCCSPs.

Figure 9: The deformation modes of CCCSP-1 (numbers correspond to those in Fig. 8).

3.2 Interface enhancement

Debonding between face sheet and core is the dominant mechanism determining the failure of fabricated CACSP. In that way, the CACSP only suffered from elastic deformation and still possessed intact core which can recover after unloading and the maximum load was rather low.

To enhance the interface strength of CACSP for higher load-carrying property, a polypropylene glue stick with a diameter of 5 mm was used as a pin into every contact area of face sheet and corresponding part of unit cell to restrict the relative sliding. Firstly, a pre-fabricated hole was drilled after which no visible crack is observed and the polypropylene stick was cut into desired segments. Then, put the polypropylene segment into the hole and kept two ends of segment a bit out of the structure. Finally, used electric soldering iron to melt the polypropylene glue segment and press on it to form a hat-shaped polypropylene region. There are two polypropylene glue segment locating in the center of circular direction and equally spaced in axial direction of every contact area. The drilling process and prepared PPGSR CACSP specimens are shown in Fig. 10. Generally speaking, the inner part of polypropylene glue segment helps restrict the circular sliding and the outer hat-shaped part contributes to limit the separation of face sheet and core.

(a) Drilling of CACSP

(b) Polypropylene glue stick reinforcement

(c) Fabricated PPGSR CACSP

Figure 10: Process (a) drilling and (b) polypropylene glue stick reinforcement and (c) prepared PPGSR CACSPs.

PPGSR CACSP showed a quiet extended “hardening” stage after the linear stage (Fig. 11). Different with the sharp drop after linear stage caused by adhesive debonding of CACSP, drops with small amplitude appeared from approximate 10 mm to 20 mm due to local debonding and its propagation was found for PPGSR CACSP. Polypropylene glue segments played a vital role in prohibiting interface debonding from spreading to the whole contact area between face sheet and corresponding unit cell such that the shear force was transmitted to polypropylene glue segments. Note that the shear strength is only 3 MPa of adhesive and 39 MPa of polypropylene. Accordingly, the bending resistance both in load-carrying limit and maximum displacement before failure of CACSP was much higher enhanced (Fig. 11), even corresponded to CSP in maximum displacement before failure. It shown that sandwich effect became prominent after reinforcing while stiffness was slightly lower than that of CACSP because of the drilling holes upon the face sheets.

Figure 11: The load versus displacement curves of PPGSR CACSPs along with those of CACSPs.

The typical failure modes of PPGSR CACSPs, namely core crushing, global slip and face sheet crushing, were listed in Fig. 12. For PPGSR CACSP specimen 1, sharp drop was also found at ~37 mm due to the crushing of central unit cell. Along with the loading, the load increased till another abrupt drop was met due to the global slip between pressure head and specimen on account of hat-shaped regions (Fig. 12b). Afterwards, the face sheet become the main load-carrying part and is crushed in the end (Fig. 12c). For specimen 2, global slip and face sheet crushing appeared while only global slip was found for specimen 3. Notably, no damage of polypropylene glue stick and area surrounded is found

Figure 12: Typical failure modes of PPGSR CACSPs.

Besides, PPGSR method was conducted on the tested CACSP with interface debonding to distinguish the contribution of PPGSR method and adhesive bonding method. The load versus curve and the deformation is not listed here for brevity. The peak load and stiffness are 849 N and 94 N/mm respectively which are close to those average values of CACSPs namely 1013 N and 88 N/mm. It indicated that PP glue stick is the determining factor for CACSP specimens subjected to three-point-bending. Parametric study such as the material and spatial distribution of glue stick using finite element analysis and analytical prediction concerning different failure modes will need conducting in this vein.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two kinds of curved corrugated sandwich panels with axial and circular cores along with solid panels were fabricated by hot-pressing method. Three-point-bending testing was conducted to investigate the effects of configurations and interface property on structural bending resistance and deformation.

1) Among the three configurations, solid panel are found to possess the highest peak load as 5 times as curved axial corrugated sandwich panel and almost as 2 times as curved circular one. On the contrary, the stiffness of solid panel is the lowest with the value of 80 N/mm while those of curved corrugated sandwich panel with axial and circular cores are 127 N/mm and 346 N/mm respectively due to higher cross sectional moment of inertia.

2) Adhesive bonding strength is a critical factor which limits the peak force of curved corrugated sandwich panel subjected to three-point-loading especially for the axial ones. The curved axial corrugated core merely suffered from recoverable deformation and remained almost intact after unloading while local indentation appeared to the front face sheet. In that way, it is not a desirable choice since not all material in sandwich panel contribute to resisting deformation and carrying load.

3) Polypropylene glue stick reinforcement is an effective method to enhance the interface strength and further heighten the bending resistance of curved axial corrugated sandwich panel. Polypropylene is the same material with matrix used in the curved structures above which makes it possible to recycle the whole structure without other component different from original fiber and matrix. Note that polypropylene is a widely used thermoplastic polymer with relatively low strength in engineering fields. Other stronger thermoplastic polymer such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyoxymethylene (POM) and so on, can be candidates for reinforced stick if stronger material is used for sandwich structure and better structural performance is expected.

4) After introducing polypropylene glue stick reinforcement, the resisting region before failure is quite extended where load also remains at a higher level which is beneficial for the bending resistance of curved axial corrugated sandwich panel. Though higher peak load value is reached for curved circular corrugated sandwich panel compared with axial one, gradually collapse of structure is observed after initial failure and the load stays in a low level. It can be reasonable choice to use glue stick reinforcement method to improve structural performance in the latter stage of loading for curved circular corrugated sandwich panel.

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